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THE MULTIPLE TOYS DESIGN FOR AUTISM CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Toys are important media in child development, and it is also essential for the child with autism who has difficulties in interaction behaviors. This research will find out the different level of Stimulation, and to improve the prototype of multiple toys. The results are as follows: In the parent-autistic child interaction, (A) The Physical features that effect upon 「Smiling and laughing」 : features are fine weave fabrics and low density in tactile sense and shimmer fabrics in visual sense. (B) The Physical features that effect upon 「Eyes contact」 : features are smoothness weave in surface - low density in tactile sense and shimmer fabrics in visual sense. (C) The Physical features that effect upon 「Concentration」 : features are the thickness weave surface in tactile Sense and glossiness fabrics in visual sense . (D) The Physical features that effect upon 「Finger indicating」 : thin fabrics weave in tactile sense and glossiness in visual sense.

Keywords: Toy design, Autism, Interaction .

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Since Leo Kanner published the first research paper on autism in 1943, people have widely associated impaired social interaction, impaired linguistic communication, and restricted and repetitive behaviors with autism as its major symptoms. According to early pathological research, two to five in every 10,000 children are autism patients (Lotter, 1966; Wing & Gould, 1979). However, according to more recent research (Baird, Charman et al., 2000),

actually 40 to 60 in every 10,000 children suffer from autism, including atypical autism or autistic spectrum disorders (ASD). These findings indicate the number of autism patients has been increasing in recent years.

In 1969, Dr. Jean Ayres from the University of Southern California proposed the concept of sensory integration, suggesting that each child is naturally equipped with the functions of sensory integration. However, only when children's brains and bodies continuously adapt and respond to the environment through interactions with it can their sensory integration functions develop healthily (Chen , 1994). In his *Sensory Integration and Children Development—Theory and Application*, Luo (1998) indicated "Provision of stimuli that autistic children prefer or accept can help to enhance their willingness to participate in activities, improve their cerebral functions of sensory processing, and enable proper responses." developed a toy prototype with compound sensory stimuli (proprioceptional, tactile, visual, olfactory, and audio). However, their research found even though the prototype did not significantly enhance the interactions between the surveyed autistic children and their parents, it still helped to maintain a certain level of interactions between them. In addition, the research also found five of the surveyed children had different responses to different sensory stimuli and the effects of their interactions with their parents varied based on different sensory integration. Among the stimuli, the proprioceptional, tactile and visual ones are found to have relatively significant influences on the interactions between autistic children and their children. These findings are worthy of further examination and discussion.

1.2 RESEARCH PURPOSE

This study is composed of the following three components:

1. Scales were established to measure the physical properties of different types of sensory stimuli. The scales were then evaluated and selected by experts and then used to provide references for the design of the toy prototypes of this research.
2. The prototypes that combine different stimuli were made and then used in experiments to explore how they affect the parent-child interactions.
3. Records of the experiments were made and then analyzed using Quantification I method to find out how the autistic children and the parents react to stimuli of corresponding type of physical properties.

1.3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study was conducted in the following two steps:

1. Establishing the physical properties of the toys

After the evaluations and selections by the experts, MDS was used to find out the textiles that best represents the tactile and visual stimuli. The textiles were then applied to the toy prototypes.

2. Experiments of parent-child interactions

Experiments using the prototypes were conducted and recorded to explore how the children interacted with their parents when playing the prototypes and how the parents perceive. The Quantification I method developed by Hayashi (1950) was used to analyze the weighted relationships between the subjects and the physical properties of the toy prototypes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 AUTISTIC DISORDER

The term "autism" was first used by Eugen Bleuler, a Swiss psychiatrist, in 1908 to describe schizophrenic patients who had once been normal people but suddenly had difficulties communicating with others and suffered from extreme isolation. The major three features of autism are as follows:

1. Impaired social interaction
2. Impaired linguistic communication
3. Restricted and repetitive behaviors

Generally, autism can be divided into three categories: high function, medium function, and low function based on the patient's intelligence,

linguistic communication capability and social adaptation level.

2.2 SENSORY SYSTEM AND LEARNING CAPABILITY

A sensory system mainly consists of the vestibular system, proprioceptional, tactile, visual, audio, and olfactory sections. Among all the sensory stimuli, proprioceptional, tactile and visual ones have significant influences on the interactions between autistic children and their parents (Ma & Su · 2008). Just like Ma and Su's research, 300g volleyballs were also used as the base of the toy prototypes in this study onto the surface of which tactile and visual stimuli were attached. The connections between tactile and visual stimuli and learning capability are described as follows:

(1) Tactile Stimuli

Tactile stimuli occur the most frequently. There are countless signals continuously transmitted via the skin, muscles, and joints to the brain, which then deciphers senses of touch, orientation, pressure and weight.

Before the experiments in this study, those children with sensitive tactile senses were massaged on their limbs and bodies to gradually reduce their sensitivity while those children with dull tactile senses were brushed on their skin or given toys for them to touch or grab in order to enhance their tactile senses.

Autistic patients have poor learning capability about tactile senses and also poor detection of different levels of tactile senses. However, they can still receive signals of tactile signals. If they can accept the stimuli, then they can learn well about the stimuli. If not, they will not react to the stimuli no matter how much stimulated. Therefore, when selecting the tactile stimuli and their strength, it is necessary to choose those stimuli acceptable to autistic children.

(2) Visual Stimuli

The autistic children in this study were observed in ball throwing and catching games and in writing exercises to measure their visual acuity, recognition of shapes, positions and orientations as well as their eye-hand coordination. Autistic children tend to avoid eye contacts with others and lack in the ability and willingness to explore and learn about the

surrounding environments. Therefore, only by providing visual stimuli that autistic children like or accept can their recognition ability be improved.

Based on the sensory integration theory, this study first defined the physical properties of the tactile and visual stimuli used in developing the toy prototypes and then discussed about the effects of the prototypes on the interactions between the surveyed autistic children and their parents.

2.3 THERAPEUTIC GAMES OF PARENT-CHILD INTERACTIONS

A family is an epitome of a society. Parents are those whom their children are the closest with. According to John Bowlby, a British psychiatrist who first formulated the theory of attachment, attachment is a kind of strong emotional connections between infants and their major caretakers. It is the earliest interpersonal relationship in one’s life. Building attachment between parents and children through parent-child interactions is particularly important for families with autistic children (Yang, Huang and Wang, 2002).

Therefore, games between parents and autistic children are important for the following reasons:

- 1.The games help to keep the children in their best conditions of alertness, not feeling too dull or too excited in the games;
2. The games enable the children and parents to interact intensively and provide them a channel to build attachment between each other.
- 3.The games encourage the children to explore the surrounding environments.
- 4.The games encourage the children to participate more closely in social and linguistic communication.

III. PRE-EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

30 designers were invited to participate in the pre-experiment to evaluate and select repetitive tactile and visual stimuli. There were two parts in this pre-experiment. The first part was selecting terms of representative tactile and visual stimuli while the second one was the evaluation of textile samples for the balls.

3.1 SELECTING REPRESENTATIVE ADJECTIVES OF TACTILE AND VISUAL PERCEPTIONS

Totally 93 representative adjectives about textures were extracted from “A Study on the relationship between Texture Image and Textile Fabrics of Bags” (Hong, 1999) and “The Influence of Image on the Sense of sight and Touch: A Case Study of Plastics Material Etching” (Lu, 2002). 25 experts were invited to select from these 93 adjectives to find out representative adjectives of tactile and visual perceptions. The selection was divided into two stages:

1. Each of the experts was requested to select 20 representative adjectives of visual and tactile perceptions. The selected adjectives were then collected and those selected by less than 10 experts (1/3 of the experts) were excluded. In the end, totally 25 representative adjectives were selected.
- 2.Six textile samples selected by experts were used as examples. 30 subjects were invited to evaluate the adjectives based on the textile samples using a 7-point Likert scale. The evaluation results were analyzed using hierarchical cluster analysis to divide the adjectives into eight clusters (See Figure1).

Figure 1. Clusters of the Adjectives

3. The center of each cluster was calculated and the adjective with the smallest scores was the most representative in each cluster. They were: soft, round, light, lively, glossy, transparent, cold, and rough.

3.2 EVALUATION OF TEXTILE SAMPLES

Experts with professional textile backgrounds were invited to select 20 representative textile samples. Then 30 designers were invited to the experiments of

tactile and visual perceptions of the samples. The experiment results were analyzed using MDS method and six of the samples were selected to coat the volleyballs with. The coated balls were then used in the experiments of parent-child interactions.

There were two stages in this section:

1. Tactile and Visual Perception Experiments of the Textile Samples

(1).Tactile Perception:30 subjects with professional design background were invited to touch without seeing the 20 textile samples. Then they used the eight adjectives to describe the tactile perception each textile sample caused. The 20 samples were divided into three clusters (strong, medium, and weak), based on the strength of the tactile perceptions they caused. Then the samples in each cluster were ranked. (See Figure 2.)

(2).Visual Perception: The subjects were asked to watch the textile samples without touching them. Then they used the eight adjectives to describe the visual perception each textile sample caused. The 20 samples were divided into three clusters (strong, medium, and weak), based on the strength of the visual perceptions they caused. Then the samples in each cluster were ranked.

Figure 2. A Scene of the Tactile Perception Experiment

2. Strength of Tactile and Visual Perceptions Caused by Textile Samples.

The results of the tactile and visual perceptions of the 20 textile samples were analyzed using MDS to find out the connections between the textiles and the perceptions. The analysis results are as follows:

(1) Tactile Perception: The strength of the tactile perception each textile sample caused was used as

input data for the MDS analysis. The X-axis corresponded to the "textile surface density level" ranging from loose to dense while the Y-axis to the "textile thickness level" ranging from thick to thin.

Figure 3. MDS Results of Textile Samples' Tactile Perceptions

(2)Visual Perception: The strength of the visual perception each textile sample caused was used as input data for the MDS analysis. The X-axis corresponded to the "textile surface brightness level" ranging from bright to dark while the Y-axis to the "textile surface smoothness level" ranging from rough to smooth.

Figure 4. MDS Results of Textile Samples' Visual Perceptions

Based on the MDS results that show the correlations of the textile samples in terms of perception strength levels (Figures 3 and 4), six representative textile samples were selected to coat the balls with. The following is a short description about the connections between the textile samples and the strength of visual and tactile perceptions they could cause:

Samples causing stronger tactile perception than visual perception: flannel (Sample 3) and suede (Sample 5) .Samples causing stronger visual perception than tactile perception: flax textile (Sample 4) and canvas (Sample 17)

Samples causing visual and tactile perceptions of equal strength: sequined textile (Sample 15) and fuzzy textile (Sample 16)

Properties Sample	Tactile				Visual			
	Loose	Dense	Thick	Thin	Bright	Dark	Smooth	Rough
Fuzzy Textile		V	V			V		V
Sequined Textile	V			V	V			V
Flax Textile	V		V			V		V
Canvas		V	V			V		V
Suede and Flannel		V	V			V	V	

Table 1. Tactile and Visual Properties of the Six Representative Textile Samples

IV. PARENT-CHILD INTERACTION EXPERIMENT

4.1 EXPERIMENT DESIGN

The selected six textiles were used to coat 300g volleyballs to produce the toy prototypes used in the parent-child interaction experiment. There were seven 30-minute interaction sessions on different days totally in the experiment. Totally 15 autistic children participated in the experiment along with their parents. In the first session, volleyballs without any textile coating were used and in the rest of the six sessions, volleyballs coated with the six textiles were used respectively in each session. In each session, one of the parents played the volleyball with the child while the other parent was responsible for recording the child's (1) smiling and laughing frequency; (2) eye contact frequency; (3) attentiveness level; and (4) frequency of pointing things with his or her fingers. After each session, the parent who played with the child was responsible for filling out Questionnaire B, answering questions about (1) how much the child enjoyed himself in the session; (2) how active the child was in the session; and (3) how the child responded to the session. The parent answered the questions using a five-point scale with one indicating "very poor" and five indicating "very good".

Figure 5. Photos of the Parent-Child Interaction Experiment

4.2 EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

From the experiment of seven interaction sessions, this study intended to

- (1) explore the influences of the toy prototypes with compound sensory stimuli of different strength levels on the interactions between autistic children and their parents;
- (2) analyze and find out the corresponding physical properties of different sensory stimuli; and
- (3) evaluate and explore the correlations between parent-child interaction and parents' perceptions.

4.2.1 Influence of the Toy Prototypes on Parent-Child Interaction

1. Correlation between Smiling/laughing Frequency and Tactile Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X1_textile surface density level	loose	22	0.822
	dense	-11	
X2_thickness level	thick	-4.5	0.683
	thin	22.5	

Multiple correlation

coefficient (r) = 0.941

Coefficient of Determination (r²)= 0.886

The “textile surface density level” had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.822) while the score of “loose” was higher (22) than that of “dense”. As indicated in Table 3, sequined textiles and flax textiles have the physical property of looseness. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.941, indicating high correlation between the child’s smiling/laughing frequency between tactile stimuli.

Correlation between Smiling/laughing Frequency and Visual Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X3_glossiness level	bright	45	0.793
	dark	-9	
X4_textile surface smoothness level	smooth	1	0.046
	rough	-0.5	

Multiple correlation coefficient (r) = 0.806

Coefficient of Determination (r²) = 0.649

The “glossiness level” had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.793) while the score of “bright” was higher (45). According to Table 3, sequined textiles had the physical property of brightness. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.806, indicating high correlation between the child’s smiling and laughing and the visual stimuli.

2. Eye contact frequency and tactile stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X1_textile surface density level	loose	35.833	0.492
	dense	-17.916667	
X2_thickness level	thick	5.333	0.257
	thin	-26.666667	

Multiple correlation coefficient (r) = 0.5

Coefficient of Determination (r²) = 0.25

The “textile surface density level” had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.492) and the score of “loose” was the higher (35.833). As indicated in Table 3, sequined textiles and flax textiles had the physical property of looseness. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.5, indicating moderate correlation.

Correlation between Eye Contact Frequency and Visual Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X3_glossiness level	bright	17.5	0.190
	dark	-3.5	
X4_textile surface smoothness level	smooth	16.667	0.280
	rough	-8.333	

Multiple correlation

coefficient (r) = 0.297

Coefficient of Determination (r²) = 8.809

The “smoothness level” had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.28) while the score of “smooth” had the higher score (16.667). According to Table 3, the textiles that have the physical property of smoothness are suede and flannel. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.297, indicating low correlation.

3. Correlation between Attentiveness Level and Tactile Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X1_textile surface density level	loose	3.833	0.297
	dense	-1.917	
X2_thickness level	thick	3.667	0.686
	thin	-18.333	

Multiple correlation coefficient (r)

Coefficient of Determination (r²) = 0.505

The “thickness level” had the higher partial correlation coefficient while the score of “thick” was higher (3.667) than “thin”. According to Table 3, the textiles that have the physical property of thickness are fuzzy textiles, flax textiles, canvas, suede, and flannel. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.711, indicating high correlation.

Correlation between Attentiveness Level and Visual Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X3_glossiness level	bright	-19.167	0.928
	dark	3.833	
X4_textile surface smoothness level	smooth	-9.333	0.887
	rough	4.667	

Multiple correlation coefficient (r) = 0.94

Coefficient of Determination (r²) = 0.884

The “glossiness level” had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.928) while the score of “dark” was higher (3.833). As indicated in Table 3, the textiles that have the physical property of darkness are fuzzy textiles, flax textiles, canvas, suede, and flannel. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.94, indicating high correlation.

4. Correlation between Pointing with Fingers and Tactile Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X1_textile surface density level	loose	2.833	0.234
	dense	-1.417	
X2_thickness level	thick	-1.5	0.374
	thin	7.5	

Multiple correlation coefficient (r) = 0.604

Coefficient of Determination (r^2) = 0.364

The "thickness level" had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.374) while the score of "thin" was higher (7.5) than "thick". According to Table 3, sequined textiles have the physical property of thinness. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.604, indicating moderate correlation.

Correlation between Pointing with Fingers and Visual Stimuli

Item	Categories	Score	r ²
X3_glossiness level	bright	10.556	0.561
	dark	-2.111	
X4_textile surface smoothness level	smooth	0.444	0.045
	rough	-0.222	

Multiple correlation coefficient (r) = 0.573

Coefficient of Determination (r^2) = 0.329

The "glossiness level" had the higher partial correlation coefficient (0.561) while the score of "bright" was higher (10.556). According to Table 3, the textiles that have the physical property of "brightness" are sequined textiles. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.573, indicating moderate correlation.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Ma & Su (2008) found in their research each of the five surveyed autistic children had different responses to different sensory stimuli and the combination of different sensory stimuli could affect the interactions between the children and their parents. They found proprioceptional, tactile, and visual stimuli have relatively significant influences on the parent-child interactions. From the analyzed questionnaire and experiment results, this study would like to offer the following suggestions regarding the production of toys that combine different sensory stimuli of different strength levels to enhance the interactions between autistic children and their parents:

1. Encouraging smiling and laughing: textiles that are loosely knit, such as sequined and flax textiles, and/or textiles that are glossy, such as sequined

textiles, can be used to produce toys that can encourage smiling and laughing of the autistic children. Glossy objects such as sequins and beads can also be used to enhance the effects.

2. Encouraging eye contacts: loosely knit textiles, such as sequined and flax textiles, and/or textiles with smooth surfaces, such as suede and flannel can be used to produce toys that can encourage eye contacts between the autistic children and their parents. Silk and cotton threads can also be used to produce a smooth and loosely knit surface to achieve the effects.

3. Encouraging attentiveness: textiles relatively thick or dark can be used in toys to encourage the attentiveness of autistic children in playing the games. Among the six representative textiles, only sequined textiles are not thick or dark. Therefore, in designing toys for autistic children, thick and lackluster textiles can be used to enhance their attentiveness in playing with the toys.

4. Encouraging pointing with fingers: thin and glossy textiles can be used to produce toys to encourage the children to point things with their fingers. Among the six representative textiles, only sequined textiles are thin and glossy. In addition, in designing toys for autistic children, thin, glowing or glossy materials can be used to increase their interest and take active actions in playing with the toys.

According to the experiment results in this study, toys that combine multiple sensory stimuli can induce different responses from the children. Stimuli that can enhance the children attentiveness in playing with the toys may interfere with and then reduce their interactions with their parents.

Based on the findings of this study, future research may explore the design of different types of toys that can enhance and stimulate autistic children's responsiveness and interactions with others.

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